

IMPROVING RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN PARTICIPANTS IN THE INVESTMENT AND CONSTRUCTION PROCESS

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Abstract. *The purpose of the article is to optimize construction time, which today is considered one of the most complex and controversial problems in the investment and construction sector. The reduction in construction time is primarily the result of the economic interest of participants in the investment and construction process. The source of economic interest of construction participants is the receipt of benefits from each of them, that is, the customer service, the design organization, and the general contracting construction organization. An important direction for improving the standardization of construction time is the further development of elements of economic and contract construction methods.*

Keywords: *construction duration, production method, construction participants, economic effect.*

Introduction. The development of the construction industry is directly related to the improvement of the regulatory and technical framework, which forms the basis for assessing the effectiveness of the investment and construction process as a whole. In this regard, the Development Strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 sets the goal "...Improving technical regulation in the construction sector" [1]. Currently, in the construction industry there are cases of deterioration in the quality of commissioned facilities, overestimation of the cost of construction work and an unreasonable increase in construction time. One of the systemic reasons for these shortcomings is a significant lag in updating the technical regulation of urban planning activities [2]. In particular, this concerns the duration of the investment and construction process as a whole and the norms for the duration of construction of facilities. Standardization of construction duration must have a solid methodological basis, extensive information practice and take into account the possibility of using modern methods and technologies of construction production. The country's leadership is taking active measures to improve technical regulation in construction [3]. Organizational measures must be supported by scientific and methodological developments that help substantiate regulatory and technical requirements. One of the current areas for improving technical regulation is improving methods and tools for increasing the investment and construction process. Standardization of construction duration must have a solid methodological basis, extensive information practice and take into account the possibility of using modern methods and technologies of construction production. The country's leadership is taking active measures to improve technical regulation in construction [3]. Organizational measures must be supported by scientific and methodological developments that

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Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. As is known, the creation of construction products involves the fulfillment of a triune task, which characterizes the fulfillment of the following interrelated requirements: implementation of the project with the required level of quality, within the allocated volumes of investment and on time. At the same time, the requirement to implement the project on time has a decisive influence on two other elements, that is, on the quality and final cost of the construction project.

The investment and construction process represents the orderliness of actions to achieve investment goals, which ensure the efficiency of the activities of all construction participants. The full cycle of the investment and construction process includes the following stages: establishing investment goals and allocating the necessary funds, pre-design work, design of construction projects, organization of construction (logistics, construction work, installation of technological equipment, running-in of the component parts of the facility, operation).

The main factor influencing the efficiency of the investment and construction process is the distribution of responsibility between construction participants. The model of distribution of responsibility in each investment project is called the method of organizing construction. There are many options for organizing construction. At the same time, two extreme opposite points of construction methods can be distinguished: the economic method and the contract method.

In the economic method of organizing construction, all powers and responsibilities are concentrated on the investor, who is also the developer, that is, the owner of the land plot on which construction is planned. The investor, due to its isolation, performs the functions of a customer, design, construction and operating organization. All work is carried out by the forces and means of existing enterprises or organizations.

The economic method in its pure form is rare. Typically, large manufacturing enterprises use it to update fixed assets, technical re-equipment, and sometimes to reconstruct individual production facilities.

The advantages of the economic method of construction include full satisfaction of the investor's requirements, independent establishment of construction deadlines, flexible provision of construction resources, consistency of all stages of the investment and construction cycle. The disadvantages of this method are the low qualifications of the performers and, as a rule, the low quality of the finished object, increased construction costs, and reduced efficiency of actions at the stages of the investment and construction process.

The contract production method is the opposite of the economic method. In it, all stages of the investment and construction process are distributed between independent economic entities that interact on the basis of contractual relations. For example, an investor is bound by an agreement with the customer, who in turn has an agreement with the design and general contractor. Similarly, relationships with resource suppliers, subcontractors, supervisory authorities and credit institutions are also built on a contractual basis. Each construction participant has his own material interest and obligations under the contracts.

The undoubted advantages of the contract construction method are the high competence of construction participants, mutual control of the fulfillment of contractual obligations, ensuring construction in the required time frame within the limits of investment volumes. In addition, with the contract construction method, market relations appear in the investment and construction process.

The disadvantages of the contracting method include the bureaucratization of relations between construction participants, the difficulty of resolving controversial issues, and the discrepancy between the economic interests of each participant and the general goals of the investment project. It should be noted that to overcome these shortcomings, construction participants use various methods of cooperation, for example: combining the functions of the customer and developer, creating design and construction associations, etc.

The total duration of an investment project is determined as the sum of the durations of all stages. At the same time, the interests of the investor involve determining the optimal (shortest from an organizational and technical point of view) period for the implementation of the investment project, which involves combining work on individual stages of the project.

Consequently, reducing the duration of the investment and construction process includes several areas: accelerating the time frame for developing a feasibility study for a project, reducing the time required for approval of various aspects of design and construction activities, reducing the time required for designing a facility, and reducing the duration of construction. (Table 1)

Table 1.

Key indicators of the duration of the investment and construction process

No.	Name	Project Duration Indicators	Combining stages
1	Feasibility study	Directive deadline for implementation Return on capital	After making a decision to implement the project, the customer can begin preliminary research
2	Pre-project stage	Clarified target date for project implementation	The signing of an investment agreement creates a legal basis for the start of engineering surveys by the design organization

3	Design	Comparison of construction duration options by construction organization	Combining the interests of design and construction organizations creates conditions for parallel work.
4	Construction	Establishing construction deadlines according to the organizational and technological model	The use of advanced technologies and modern materials helps reduce construction time.

The duration of construction is part of the overall life cycle of the investment project. However, this part is considered the most complex and prone to risk factors. Firstly, technical and technological limitations determine the possibilities of using advanced methods and limit the attraction of additional material and technical resources. Secondly, organizational and economic conditions and the uncertainty of construction production make the construction stage vulnerable to external negative factors. Thirdly, along with the design stage, construction is a sphere of manifestation of the economic interests of many entities that are objectively participants in the investment and construction process.

Discussion. Determining the optimal duration of construction is one of the most important stimulating indicators of the activities of participants in the investment process. The use of advanced methods of organizing production, the use of modern building materials and mechanization, as well as the introduction of new technologies for the production of work have a positive impact on construction time and create conditions for their reduction.

The question arises: how to use the positive aspects of each method of organizing construction? It is necessary to develop a mechanism for optimally combining powers and responsibilities in the investment and construction process. Currently, the problem of forming a construction cluster is widely covered in the scientific press. In our opinion, this should be justified not only on the basis of the great efficiency of clusters in agriculture and industry, but also on an in-depth study of the organizational and economic interests of construction participants.

The use of industrial construction methods, modern efficient materials, and a reduction in the share of wet processes helps to reduce the time required for construction work. At the same time, the strengthening of the role of customers in the investment and construction process leads to the fact that construction deadlines are set not for technological reasons, but based on investment considerations and the need to return capital investments.

Fulfillment of the requirements of investors and customers is possible only if they do not contradict the economic interests of other participants. Reforming relations between participants in the investment and construction process must comply with the principles of marketization, mutual recognition of interests, priority of common goals, equality of powers, and efficiency of decision-making.

Compliance with these principles presupposes the widespread use in construction of network and information models for the formation of the construction process. In addition, it is necessary to develop a mechanism for managing the investment and construction process based on continuous improvement of methods of organizing construction.

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